

Validation of vibrotactile feedback to improve selective motor units recruitment

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Abstract—Recently, muscle interfaces have been used to control external devices through the activation of single motor units. In the present study, we proposed and validated two different vibrotactile feedback strategies designed to convey information about the firing rate of two motor units active at the same time. In a two-alternative forced-choice task, participants had to discriminate the higher vibration frequency among the ones of two vibrotactile stimulators placed on their arms. *Spike strategy* and *continuous strategy* were tested in two different experiments and motor units' activation was simulated. The *spike strategy* directly translates the discharge activity of motor units into a vibratory burst with a 1-to-1 conversion, i.e. each spike of one motor unit triggers a single burst of the corresponding vibrator. This was evaluated in two body configurations, i.e. same forearm versus different arms. The *continuous strategy* mapped the discharge activity of motor units into a continuous vibration exploiting the entire operative range of vibrotactile stimulators. A single-body configuration was tested (i.e. two different arms). Participants' responses were fitted with a psychometric sigmoid curve (i.e. a psychometric model commonly applied to detection and discrimination tasks), and the discrimination accuracy index was used to evaluate the feedback strategies. Results from Experiment 1 showed that the *continuous strategy* worked better when the stimulators were placed on two different arms, but overall discrimination performance was poor. Experiment 2 showed that both the *continuous strategy* conveyed vastly superior overall performance compared to the *continuous strategy*.

Index Terms—Wearable Device, Vibrotactile Feedback, Psychometric Measures, Motor Units, Augmentation

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the topic of human movement augmentation (i.e., the enhancement of motor performance beyond the level

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of able-bodied human beings), has become increasingly relevant in the field of bioengineering [1], [2] and often consists in providing the user with supernumerary robotic limbs (i.e., fingers or arms) that can grant new ways to interact with the environment.

A pivotal aspect is the ability to effectively control additional degrees-of-freedom (DoF) concurrently with natural movements. A common approach to deal with this aspect is to measure physiological parameters, such as electromyographic (EMG) activity, from the human body [3] and use them as a controlling signal for the robotic effector.

However, to achieve human augmentation, participants should be able to voluntarily manipulate these physiological parameters without interfering with natural motion. To face this fundamental issue, neuroscientific research is exploring the concept of “null space”. A change in a physiological signal from the null space does not produce a movement in the body, or if it does, it does not affect the end-effector state [4].

In the context of human augmentation, motor units (MUs) null space has been investigated through real-time algorithms that extract motor units' activity by using high-density surface electromyography (HD-sEMG) recordings. With this non-invasive methodology, authors of [5] investigated whether participants could learn how to flexibly and independently recruit different MUs to control a cursor on a screen. So far, to induce leaning in the control of motor units only visual feedback has been provided to participants. However, exploiting somatosensory feedback could provide important benefits, especially in the framework of human augmentation [6], [7], such as relieving participants from constant visual monitoring of the controlled device, which could be cognitively demanding [8], and providing information with higher sensory processing speed [9] compared to vision.

In the present work, we validated different strategies to relay information concerning the activation of different motor units. To be more specific, we assessed participants' ability to

discriminate between two different simultaneous vibrations, delivered by two stimulators that closely replicate the simulated activity of two motor units. Using a two-alternative forced-choice paradigm, we investigated in the first experiment the feasibility of a novel bio-inspired feedback where the stimulators were repeatedly activated in short bursts (i.e., 15 ms each burst) to simulate the frequency at which motor units discharge action potentials. Additionally, in the second experiment, we tested the possibility to convey the MUs' firing rate by modulating the frequency of continuous vibration.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Participants

In each experiment, five healthy volunteers were enrolled (3 females). The average age of participants was 25.2 ± 3.3 years in Experiment 1 and 23.8 ± 0.5 years in Experiment 2. All participants provided written informed consent before starting the study. Experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with the declaration of Helsinki and following amendments and approved by the Ethical Committee of Università Campus Bio-Medico di Roma (HUROB protocol).

B. Experimental Setup

Participants comfortably sat on a chair with their arms laid back on the armrests and their hands' palms down. The subject was then required to wear headphones delivering white noise to avoid any auditory cues from the motors. Vibration feedback was provided through a vibrotactile stimulation interface previously developed and here further optimized, [7].

The wearable interface was composed of two Eccentric Rotating Mass (ERM) motors (Model: 307-103 by Precision Microdrives Inc.) and a custom Printed Circuit Board (PCB). The PCB consisted of a compact ($6 \times 6 \text{ cm}^2$) wearable device that enables independent control of up to 6 motors. The Board incorporated h-bridge drivers (L2293Q, STMicroelectronics Inc) and a microcontroller (μC) (STM32F446RET6, STMicroelectronics Inc).

In the present study, only two vibrator motors were employed and fixed on participants' arms using medical tape.

To let the experimenter set the type of feedback modality, frequency, and activation timing of the stimulators, we implemented a graphical user interface (GUI) using C++ language in Qt Creator 8.0.1 environment. The μC , based on information coming from the control GUI through serial communication, modulated the vibration intensity by generating a Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signal. The input voltage applied to the motors was proportional to the duty cycle of the signal as defined by the following equation:

$$V_s(t) = \delta(t)V_m, \quad (1)$$

where V_s is the supply voltage of the stimulator, $\delta(t)$ is the duty cycle of the PWM, and V_m is the supply voltage of the motor drivers. By varying the duty cycle value from 0

to 1, according to the feedback strategy, we vary the vibration intensity¹.

C. Experiment 1

In Experiment 1, we tested a "spike strategy", designed to be time-locked with the activity of selected MUs. Considering the experiment conducted by Bracklein et al. [5] as a practical implementation of this feedback, whenever the decomposition algorithm of high-density surface electromyography (HD-sEMG) would detect an action potential from the selected motor neuron, the stimulator is activated for 15 milliseconds by delivering a power supply of 3V (V_m in equation 1) and then deactivated.

In the present work, we simulated the activity of two different MUs by activating stimulators in a physiological fashion. For this purpose, we limited the frequency range at which bursts could be delivered to 4-18 Hz. Additionally, we set the difference in burst activity between the two stimulators, computed as right stimulator (RS) frequency minus left stimulator (LS) frequency, in the range $[-3, +3]$ Hz, with 1 Hz steps, resulting in 7 comparisons.

To assess the participants' ability to perceive these differences, we used a two-alternative forced-choice task, in which the two stimulators were activated simultaneously for 3 seconds. We selected a duration long enough to well perceive the lowest frequencies. Participants had to verbally report which of the two stimulators they perceived as activated at the higher frequency. The sequence of stimulation and subjects' response corresponded to one trial, and was repeated 280 times per condition (40 trials per each comparison), resulting in a total of 560 trials, with an inter-trial pause of 2 seconds (Fig. 1, Top).

To investigate the efficacy of the feedback delivered in different body location, Experiment 1 was performed in two different conditions: 1) with both stimulators on the same arm; 2) with one stimulator per arm.

In the first case, stimulators were placed on the lateral and medial aspect of the right forearm, corresponding to C7 dermatome (see Fig.1 Bottom, A); whereas in the latter condition, vibrators were placed one per arm, on the lateral aspect of the forearm (see Fig.1 Bottom, B). We selected to stimulate participants on the C7 dermatome as it was shown to be the location on the arm with the highest spatial and temporal discrimination for vibrotactile stimuli [10]. When stimulators were placed on the same arm, we ensured that they were at least 8 cm apart to minimize the impact of one stimulator's vibration on the perception of the other [11]. The two conditions were evaluated in two different sessions, in a pseudorandomized order.

D. Experiment 2

In Experiment 2 we tested a "continuous strategy" in which stimulators were activated continuously for 1.5 seconds for

¹Vibration frequency and amplitude are not independent in ERM vibrating motors, so increasing the supply voltage of the motor increases both vibration frequency and amplitude.

each trial with a vibration frequency modulated to cover the entire operating range of the motors (40 Hz - 230 Hz). Being the vibration continuous and the frequency higher, we decreased its duration with respect to Experiment 1 to avoid habituation or annoyance. To map the activity of motor units on the stimulators' operating range, we used two different approaches:

- 1 *Flat approach*: we divided the motor's bandwidth into 15 evenly spaced intervals, so that each interval corresponded to a single step on the range of MU activity (4-18 Hz with 1 Hz step) maintaining a constant, flat difference between each interval (i.e., 13.6Hz).
- 2 *Percentage approach*: similar to the *Flat approach* but instead of a fixed increase between each interval, we used a percentage increase of 13.3%, so that every step is increased by the 13.3% of the previous one. The specific percentage value to cover the entire range of MU activity was selected using the following equation:

$$f(i) = f_0(1 + p)^i, \quad i \in [0 \div 14] \quad (2)$$

Where f_0 is the lowest value of the motor's frequency (corresponding to the lowest value of MU's frequency, i.e. 4Hz), $f(i)$ is the frequency associated with the $(i + 1)^{th}$ MU's value, and $p=0.133$ is the constant percentage increment.

We reported in Figure 2 all the vibration frequencies and duty cycle values associated to MU discharge rate, for both *flat* and *percentage* approach. To assess the efficacy of this feedback strategy we adopted the same task as in Experiment 1, considering Flat and Percentage approaches as conditions instead of stimulator configuration. Based on the results from Experiment 1, in this case we considered only one configuration, i.e. one stimulator on each arm.

Fig. 1. Top: Experimental protocol. The two motors were activated for a brief amount of time (3 seconds in Experiment 1, and 1.5 seconds in Experiment 2). Participant were asked to indicate which stimulator they perceived to be vibrating at a higher frequency (right or left), typically within 1-2 seconds, followed by a brief pause. This sequence was repeated 280 times for each conditions, for a total of 560 trials in each experiment. Bottom: Stimulator's placement on two different arm for Experiment 1 and 2 (A), or on the same arm for Experiment 1 (B).

MU freq (Hz)	Flat approach		Percentage approach	
	Freq (Hz)	Duty cycle	Freq (Hz)	Duty cycle
4	40	0.1325	40	0.1325
5	53.6	0.1946	45.4	0.1572
6	67.2	0.2567	51.4	0.1846
7	80.6	0.3161	58.2	0.2156
8	94.2	0.38	66	0.2512
9	107.8	0.4421	74.8	0.2914
10	121.4	0.5042	84.6	0.3361
11	135	0.5663	96	0.3882
12	148.6	0.6284	108.6	0.4457
13	162.2	0.69	123.2	0.5124
14	175.8	0.7525	139.6	0.5873
15	189.4	0.8137	158	0.6713
16	203	0.8758	179.2	0.7681
17	216.6	0.9379	203	0.8767
18	230	1	230	1

Fig. 2. In the table is shown the relation between MU's frequency and the continuous vibration of Experiment 2. More in detail, column 1 is the MU's frequency, column 2 and 3 are respectively the stimulator's frequency and the duty cycle (see equation 1) of the PWM control signal for the flat approach. Column 4 and 5 are the same as 2-3 but for the percentage approach.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

Responses from all participants were merged for each condition of the two experiments and fit with a psychophysics sigmoid function [12] using a least-squares-based algorithm (Matlab R2022b, The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, United States). 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the estimated parameters were also calculated.

The psychometric function P (where P is the probability of "right" as answer) was defined as follows:

$$P(MUd, PSE, EA) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\frac{MUd - PSE}{0.5EA}\right)}, \quad (3)$$

denoting MUd the Motor Unit Difference (independent variable), PSE the Point of Subjective Equality and EA the Esteem Accuracy. PSE refers to the frequency difference between the two stimulators in order to be perceived as having the same frequency (i.e. 50% of chance to say "right"). EA is the inverse of the slope of the curve (with a multiplication factor of 0.5), calculate at $MUd=PSE$, and is a measure of how steep the curve is. The smaller the value of EA , the more the esteem is accurate.

IV. RESULTS

A. Experiment 1

Results of Experiment 1 are shown in Fig. 3. It is visible how participants' responses were quite spread, especially in the case of *same arm* condition. The fitting with the

Fig. 3. Results of Experiment 1, representing the psychometric curve for the "spike strategy" with stimulators on the same arm (top) or on different arms (bottom). The continuous line represents the fitted equation (as described in Equation 1), and the dots represent the mean performance of the subjects for the relative difference of MU activity. X-axis is the difference in the activation of the stimulators, computed as $RS - LS$, and expressed in Hz. Y-axis is the chance that participants report the RS as the one with the higher vibration intensity.

sigma-shaped psychometric curve was poor, not showing the characteristic s-shape in both cases. Moreover, even though one participant (participant 3, Fig. 3) reached values of 20% and 90% for the biggest frequency differences, in the *same arm* condition, the overall fitting ranged between 40% and 60%, thus very close to the situation in which subjects reply randomly. In the case of *different arms*, data were slightly less scattered and the fitting range widened to 25-70%.

The EA value obtained from the fitting was 5.96 Hz (CI 4.56-7.36 Hz) and 10.43 Hz (CI 8.10-12.77 Hz) respectively for the configuration with *different arms* and *same forearm*.

B. Experiment 2

The results of Experiment 2 are shown in Fig. 4. The performances of the two conditions are close, both ranging between 10% and 90%. A small difference emerges from the slope analysis: the curve related to the *percentage approach* (Fig. 4, Bottom) is slightly steeper than the one related to the *flat approach* (Fig. 4, Top). This is also evident from the EA values of the *percentage approach* (2.70 Hz), (CI 2.51-2.8868 Hz) which is smaller than the one of the *flat approach* (2.85 Hz), (CI 2.26-3.43 Hz) (see Eq. 3).

Fig. 4. Results of Experiment 2, representing the psychometric curve for the "continuous strategy" with using a Flat increment approach (top) or a Percentage increment approach (bottom). The continuous line represents the fitted equation (as described in Equation 2), and the dots represent the mean performance of the subjects for the relative difference of MU activity. X-axis is the difference in the activation of the stimulators, computed as $RS - LS$, and expressed in Hz for the Flat approach (top) or as percentage increment for the Percentage approach (bottom). Y-axis is the chance that participants report the RS as the one with the higher burst activity frequency.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The aim of the present study was to investigate with a psychophysical experiment based on a two-alternative forced-choice task, the most suitable strategy and arrangement on the body for conveying through vibrotactile stimulation the information related to the activation state of MUs.

The spike strategy tested in Experiment 1 is a novel way to encode information. Indeed, to the best of our knowledge, just a few studies (e.g. Sorgini [13]) adopted a similar strategy but with notable differences. In the case of Sorgini et al., they used a neuronal spiking model in order to convert the stiffness of a contact surface into a series of spikes sent to the participant through piezoelectric actuators, with different ranges of frequency and hardware compared to our work. In Experiment 1 we tested two different body locations: one stimulator on each forearm or both stimulators on the same forearm (on C7 dermatome). Both cases (see Fig. 3) showed a trend which is far from the typical s-shape of psychometric curves and a central part quite flat. In particular, in the same arm configuration, performances were always

close to random choice. As regard the performance of the single participants (coloured dots, Fig. 3, top), increasing the delta between the stimulators' frequency, the scattering of the data is progressively more pronounced, suggesting a low informative value of the feedback which is acting as a confounding factor. The configuration with different arms presented slightly better results both in terms of fitted curve and in terms of individual performance. Nevertheless, the outcomes are lower than expected, with the probability of an incorrect response always higher than 25%, even for the highest frequency differences.

This difference in performance between the two conditions is also observable by analyzing the estimated EA, which is higher (thus worse) in the same arm configuration rather than in the different arm one. However, in both cases, global performance was considered insufficient for conveying the desired information.

Therefore, a new strategy based on continuous vibration patterns was studied in Experiment 2. Each value of MU's firing rate in the range 4-18 Hz was associated with a well-defined continuous vibration frequency of the stimulator. In the first approach this relation was obtained by dividing all the working range of the motor into 15 equally distributed steps. In the second approach, a percentage value was calculated to move from the minimum to maximum frequency value of the motor (see eq. 2, and table 2).

Conversely to Experiment 1, in Experiment 2 participants exhibited greater accuracy and a higher percentage of correct responses in the whole frequency range, with both approaches. Indeed, the differences between performance achieved with *flat* and *percentage* strategies were relatively small.

However, it is worth noting that also in this case, the well-defined s-shape typical of the psychometric curve was not completely reached. A possible explanation could be that the limited range of frequencies evaluated in the present study (i.e., rs-ls from -3 to 3 Hz) may not be sufficient to reach the performance's plateau. It is plausible that by increasing the frequency range by a few Hz, the curve would exhibit the S-shape.

It is likely that after training, the ability of the subject to discriminate the different vibrotactile patten could increase, but this is true both in the spike strategy and in the continuous one. Given these premises, our hypothesis is that the continuous strategy will perform better even with training. In our opinion, the differences in performance of the two feedbacks cannot be ascribed to training time and are probably due to the selected hardware. Indeed, an ERM stimulator is easy to use and control, but it has some drawbacks. Firstly, the frequency and amplitude of vibration are coupled together, and it is not possible to control one independently from the other. Secondly, this type of motor has a slow dynamic, which is critical when dealing with feedback that requires the stimulator to reach the regime and then suddenly stop in the order of milliseconds, like in our case requires the spike strategy. To overcome these limitations, future studies should employ and test more performing actuators.

Summing up, in the continuous feedback strategy all participants showed higher performance in terms of accuracy and discrimination ability compared to the spike strategy. Thus, the continuous approach could be a good solution to convey information about MU's activity and help participants in learning control strategies.

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